

A COMPARISON OF NUTRIENT SOURCES, CONCENTRATIONS AND LOADING TRENDS FROM THE CUYAHOGA AND SANDUSKY RIVERS

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Introduction

The Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers are two of Ohio's major tributaries to Lake Erie. Over the past 10 years, the average-annual, unit-area export of total phosphorus (TP) to Lake Erie from these two rivers is similar, with the Cuyahoga yielding 1.36 lbs/acre at Independence and the Sandusky yielding 1.41 lbs/acre at Fremont. However, these two rivers differ substantially in the forms of phosphorus they deliver, the relationships between concentrations and stream flow, and the timing of delivery. These differences illustrate the characteristics of point source versus nonpoint source dominated streams. As such, these differences are important to keep in mind relative to total maximum daily load and nutrient trading considerations, as well as to the development of watershed action plans and assessment of their impacts on Lake Erie.

Both tributaries are part of Heidelberg University's Tributary Loading Program, which includes ten other stations in Ohio. At each station refrigerated automatic samplers are used to collect three samples per day at or near US Geological Survey gages. At weekly intervals, samples are returned to our laboratories for analyses of nutrients, selected major ions, and suspended sediments. During low flow conditions, a single sample per day is analyzed while during high flows, all three samples per day are analyzed. A map of station locations and descriptions of our analytical procedures are presented in our tributary loading web site (<http://www.heidelberg.edu/academiclife/distinctive/ncwqr/data/guide>). The sampling program on the Sandusky River was initiated in 1974 while that on the Cuyahoga River was started in 1981.

Summaries of the land use upstream from our Cuyahoga and Sandusky sampling stations are shown in Table 1. The Cuyahoga watershed upstream from the Independence gaging station is dominated by urban, suburban, and forested land uses while the Sandusky watershed is dominated by row crop agriculture.

Table 1. Land use in the Cuyahoga and Sandusky watersheds upstream from the monitoring stations.

River	USGS Station Number	Drainage Area	Agriculture-row crops	Grassland pasture	Forest	Urban/Residential	Other
		sq mile	Land use by percentage				
Cuyahoga	04208000	707	9.3	12.4	34.6	37.7	1.1
Sandusky	04198000	1251	77.7	4.3	8.8	8.0	6.0

Pollutant Export Rates

In Table 2, unit area export rates for selected pollutants from the two watersheds are shown for the time period including the 2001 to 2010 water years. These loads are based on 4,822 samples for the Cuyahoga River and 4,612 for the Sandusky River. The amount of runoff from the Cuyahoga River is larger than that of the Sandusky, apparently due to the additional runoff from lake-effect snows in the Cuyahoga watershed.

Table 2. A comparison of average annual unit area runoff and unit area export rates of suspended sediments, nutrients and chloride for the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers from the 2001 to 2010 Water Years.

River	Runoff	Suspended solids	Total Phosphorus	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus	Nitrate-N	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	Chloride
	Inches	lbs/acre					
Cuyahoga	20.8	1,323	1.36	0.21	7.64	5.2	751
Sandusky	15.0	585	1.41	0.32	18.02	5.6	91

Sediment export rates are also much higher in the urban/suburban/forested Cuyahoga watershed than for the cropland-dominated Sandusky watershed. Measurements of daily suspended sediment (SS) export by the U.S. Geological Survey (Hindall, 1989) at these same stations from 1977 to 1986 also showed higher export rates from the Cuyahoga River (1,360 lbs/acre) than for the Sandusky (1,010 lbs/acre). USGS measurements of the SS export rate at the Cuyahoga River's Old Portage gaging station (drainage area of 401 square miles) was very low (239 lbs/acre). Since the average SS export rate from the 707 square mile drainage area upstream from the Independence gaging station was 1,323 lbs per acre, very large amounts of sediment must enter the river between these two stations. The sediment exported from the Cuyahoga apparently originates from a combination of natural sources (stream beds and banks, flood plains, and steeply sloping forested soils) and urban/suburban construction sites. Cuyahoga river sediments also have larger average particle sizes and lower particulate phosphorus (PP) to SS ratios than sediment exported from the Sandusky River. SS exported from the Sandusky River is largely derived from cropland erosion.

Although the TP export rates for the Cuyahoga and Sandusky River are similar, the Sandusky has higher dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and much higher nitrate-nitrogen (nitrate) export rates. Chloride export rates for the Cuyahoga are much higher than for the Sandusky. At least some of the high chloride export from the Cuyahoga is due to road salt applications. Chloride concentrations in the Cuyahoga increase during high flow events in the winter while they decrease as flows increase in the Sandusky.

Point and Nonpoint Phosphorus Export Rates

The procedures used since the 1970s to calculate nonpoint source phosphorus export from watersheds in the Great Lakes are illustrated in Table 3. These procedures involve subtracting upstream point source inputs, as reported for NPDES permits, from TP export, as measured at tributary loading stations. The procedure assumes 100% delivery through the stream system of phosphorus from point sources. Average annual point source inputs upstream from the monitoring stations are shown in Table 3 for the period from 2006-2008. Subtracting these inputs from the average annual export for each watershed gives an estimate of the nonpoint watershed export and respective unit area exports. The agricultural Sandusky River watershed has a higher nonpoint source phosphorus export rate than the urban/suburban/forested Cuyahoga watershed.

River	Total Phosphorus Export	Upstream Point Sources	Nonpoint Source Load	Unit Area Nonpoint Load
	tons	tons	tons	lbs/acre
Cuyahoga	296	89.4	207	0.92
Sandusky	533	16.2	517	1.29

Table 3. Calculation of nonpoint source phosphorus loading from the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers based on average annual total phosphorus export for 2001 to 2010 Water Years.

Figure 1. Relationships between nutrient and suspended sediment concentrations and stream discharge for the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers for the periods from 10/1/2000 to 9/30/2010.

Relationships between Streamflow and Nutrient Concentrations

The relationships between nutrient and SS concentrations and streamflow are shown in Figure 1. These graphs include all of the data collected during the 2000 – 2010 Water Years, with up to three samples per day during high flows and one sample per day under low flows. For the Cuyahoga, DRP and nitrate concentrations decrease as flows increase (Figure 1.a. & 1.c.). This pattern reflects increasing dilution of the relatively constant daily inputs of DRP and nitrate from point source inputs as streamflows increase. For the Sandusky River, the concentrations of DRP and nitrate increase as streamflow increases (Figure 1.b. & 1.d.). In the Sandusky watershed, the dissolved nutrients are derived primarily from cropland and enter the stream as part of storm runoff water, which also increases streamflow.

The relationships between stream flow and concentrations of TP and SS for the Cuyahoga River are shown in Figures 1.e. and 1.g. respectively, while the relationships for the Sandusky River are shown in Figures 1.f. and 1.h. For both rivers, suspended solids concentrations increase with increasing streamflow. The elevated sediment concentrations during high flows reflect some combination of erosion on land surfaces associated with runoff and stream bank erosion during high stream flows. Since PP is associated with SS, PP concentrations tend to increase as SS increases. In the Sandusky River, the increasing TP with increasing streamflow also reflects the increasing DRP with streamflow. TP remains low at low stream flows in the Sandusky. For the Cuyahoga River TP is high at both high and low concentrations, reflecting sediment related PP at high flows and point source related DRP at low flows.

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It is also evident that the SS concentrations in the Cuyahoga River include many values that are much higher than is the Sandusky. The scatter in SS concentrations in the Cuyahoga River is also reflected in considerable scatter in TP concentrations.

The relationships between concentrations and streamflows shown in Figure 1 result in the flow weighted mean concentrations (FWMC) and the time weighted mean concentrations (TWMC) shown in Table 4. The FWMCs reflect the stream concentrations relative to pollutant loading to downstream receiving waters while the TWMCs reflect the concentrations relative to ambient water quality in the streams. Where concentrations increase on average with increasing stream flow, FWMCs are larger than TWMCs, as illustrated by DRP in the Sandusky River. Where concentrations decrease with increasing flows, TWMCs are larger than FWMCs as illustrated by DRP in the Cuyahoga River.

Table 4. Flow-Weighted and Time Weighted mean concentrations of suspended sediments, nutrients and chloride in the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers, 2001 to 2010 Water Years.

River	Concentration	Suspended solids	Total Phosphorus	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus	Nitrate-N	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	Chloride
mg/L							
Cuyahoga	FWMC	266	0.281	0.046	1.68	1.10	162.5
	TWMC	130	0.216	0.068	2.36	0.94	173.8
Sandusky	FWMC	167	0.396	0.087	5.62	1.67	28.7
	TWMC	65	0.186	0.048	4.11	1.07	41.5

Relationships between Streamflow and Pollutant Export

Where pollutants are derived from nonpoint sources, their export is dominated by periods of high flow. Where pollutants are derived primarily from point sources, their export tends to be significant over a much wider range of flows. These characteristics are illustrated in Table 5, which shows the proportions of the total pollutant load over the period from 2000 to 2010 that was exported by flows exceeded 10%, 20% and 50% of the time. For the Sandusky River, where DRP is derived from nonpoint sources, flows exceeded 10%, 20% and 50% of the time accounted for 66%, 84% and 98% of the DRP load. For the Cuyahoga River, where DRP export is derived primarily from point sources, the same flow exceedency periods accounted for 21%, 34% and 66% of the DRP export. The above patterns for DRP are also present for nitrate. Since sediment export from both rivers is derived primarily from nonpoint sources, high flows account for the bulk of the SS export from both rivers.

Table 5. The role of high flows in accounting for total discharge and total pollutant export from the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers for the period between 10/1/1999 and 9/30/2010

River	Discharge	Suspended solids	Total Phosphorus	Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus	Nitrate-N
% of total discharge or load from flows exceeded 10% of time					
Cuyahoga	36.8	73.0	58.1	20.7	22.3
Sandusky	55.4	77.0	72.9	66.3	53.1
% of total discharge or load from flows exceeded 20% of time					
Cuyahoga	54.1	85.3	71.2	34.2	36.1
Sandusky	74.8	90.8	88.0	83.8	74.7
% of total discharge or load from flows exceeded 50% of time					
Cuyahoga	82.1	96.4	88.5	65.8	67.1
Sandusky	93.9	98.9	98.2	97.6	95.8

Trends in Phosphorus Loading

During the period from 1982 through 2010, when loading studies have been underway in both rivers, the trends in both DRP and TP loading have been downward in Cuyahoga River while they have been upward in the Sandusky River (Figure 2.a. & 2.b. on next page). In the case of the Cuyahoga River, the downward trend in DRP loads includes rapid decreases in loading during the 1980s followed by smaller increases in loads beginning in 1999 and a leveling off in loads in 2004. These changes in DRP loading likely reflect changes in the loads from municipal sewage treatment plants as phosphorus removal programs continued. The causes of the increased loads from 1999 to 2003 are uncertain but may correspond to the onset of phosphate additions to drinking water supplies to reduce corrosion and lead release in distribution systems. The small annual variability in DRP loads from the Cuyahoga River, relative to the Sandusky River also indicates that the DRP loading in the Cuyahoga River is not greatly influenced by annual variations in runoff.

The upward trends in TP and DRP loads from the Sandusky River are influenced by a combination of increases in stream flow that have occurred during this time interval and changes in farming practices. The increases in DRP loads have been observed throughout Northwestern Ohio. Factors that have been proposed as causes of increased DRP runoff include more broadcast applications of fertilizers

in the fall, phosphorus stratification in soils in the absence of inversion tillage, increases in tile drainage density, and increased soil compaction.

The increases in DRP loading from cropland have been linked to the increasing frequency of blue-green algal blooms in Lake Erie (Ohio EPA, 2010). DRP is 100% bioavailable to algae. In contrast, particulate phosphorus is only about 30% bioavailable to algae. Furthermore, the suspended sediments which carry the bulk of the particulate phosphorus into Lake Erie, settle out of the water column quickly. Thus the particulate phosphorus associated with the suspended sediments is physically removed from water in which algae populations grow.

Implications for Management

Programs to manage nutrients are generally directed toward improving ambient water quality within streams and rivers and/or reducing nutrient loading to downstream receiving waters such as Lake Erie. In Ohio, total maximum daily load (TMDL) planning is often undertaken to bring stream and river water into compliance with Ohio's biological criteria. Biological impairments in rivers associated with elevated nutrient concentrations occur most often during low flow conditions when water moves through streams very slowly, allowing more time for the buildup of planktonic algal communities. This leads to larger diurnal fluctuations of dissolved oxygen that can increase stress on fish and invertebrate communities. Under low flow conditions, point sources are the primary source of nutrients to streams, and the resulting high loadings of dissolved nutrients can contribute to excessive algal growth. Consequently, point source controls will generally be essential to reduce the impacts of nutrient loading on ambient water quality in streams (Baker et al, 2006). Nonpoint control programs have minimal impact on nutrient concentrations during low stream flows and instead impact concentrations during high flow periods when ambient water quality programs in rivers are much less frequent. Thus TMDL planning, as well as nutrient trading programs between point and nonpoint sources, may not be appropriate for addressing ambient water quality problems in streams.

Where the goals of nutrient reduction programs are to reduce overall loading to downstream receiving waters, such as Lake Erie, TMDL planning may be more effective. However, a receiving water body may respond rather differently to equal nutrient loads, depending on how the loads are delivered. Nonpoint loads generally move into lakes in pulses having high volumes and high nutrient concentrations. An equal annual load from point sources would likely be delivered at high concentrations but in much smaller volumes at relatively equal daily loads, as opposed to loading pulses. The impact on the receiving waters could be very different depending on how the nutrient loads are delivered to the receiving waters.

Unlike the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers, where point sources dominate nutrient loads from one river and nonpoint from the other, many rivers have significant loading from both point and nonpoint sources. In such rivers, the patterns of nutrient concentrations in relation to streamflow combine both the point and nonpoint patterns. This is certainly the case where urban areas are located in watersheds that also have intense row crop agriculture. Examples of such areas abound within Ohio and include rivers such as the Scioto, Great Miami, and tributaries to the Maumee River.

Conclusions

Nutrients provide an excellent example of pollutants that are derived from both point and nonpoint sources. Often it will be essential to reduce loads from both sources. However, the patterns of nutrient concentrations and loading in streams differ greatly depending on whether the nutrients are derived from point or nonpoint sources. Where impairments of water quality due to excessive nutrient concentrations have been identified, it is essential to identify the specific sources of the nutrients that are causing the problem and treat those particular sources. Particularly where ambient water quality problems occur in rivers and streams, trading between upstream point and nonpoint sources of nutrients may not be an effective option.

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Figure 2.a.

Figure 2.b.

Figure 2. Trends in DRP and TP unit area loads from 1982 to 2010 for the Cuyahoga and Sandusky rivers.

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Abbreviations: TP (total phosphorus); DRP (dissolved reactive phosphorus); PP (particulate phosphorus); SS (suspended sediments); TKN (Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen); nitrate (nitrate-nitrogen)